

observed density $\rho_{obs} = 2.6 \text{ gml}^{-1}$. From the relation, $\rho_{obs} = \frac{1.66M.z}{V}$, the molecular weight, M , of the compound comes to 3515 against the calculated value 3544.11.

Thermal Depolymerization: The thermal depolymerization of the compound has been studied on the light of the investigations made by West and Audrieth⁶ and by Babad-Zakhryapin⁷ on a few heteropoly tungstic acids. The apparatus used for this purpose was that described by Ray and Sinha⁸ with continuous pumping the depolymerised product, followed by successive weighing using a thermogravimetric balance and estimations at some, stages. The dissociation⁵ of the compound was observed at 75° under reduced pressure when nine molecules of water were eliminated. At 125° further eleven molecules of water were lost. The rest of the eight molecules of water remained intact in the crystal lattice till 220°, above which they were completely removed. This work agreed closely with the work of Scroggie and Clark⁹ with the comparable compounds. When the temperature was raised still higher, then nearly at 350°, the compound was broken as a whole into the basic units of lower oxides of tungsten and iron which has been confirmed by analysis. So the thermal stability of 12-heteropoly tungstoferrate is 350°.

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A Test Paper Method for Detection of Sulphur Dioxide in Low Concentration by a Modified 1 : 10 Phenanthroline Reagent

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1 : 10 phenanthroline has been recommended as a sensitive reagent for the determination of sulphur dioxide by Stephens and Lindstorm¹. The method

is based on the reduction of Fe(III) to Fe(II) by sulphur dioxide and subsequent measurement of coloured complex of Fe(II) and 1 : 10 phenanthroline. The method was modified by Attari *et al.*² by using an acetate buffer. In the present method 1 : 10 phenanthroline is used with zinc acetate and sodium nitroprusside for detection of sulphur dioxide in low concentrations. Hands *et al.* have suggested a test paper impregnated with ammoniacal zinc nitroprusside for detection and determination of sulphur dioxide³. A modification of this method was done by Bourbon *et al.* by using pyridine along with zinc acetate and sodium nitroprusside⁴. The method is further modified by replacing pyridine with 1 : 10 phenanthroline. It is found that the colour obtained by 1 : 10 phenanthroline is more intense. The sensitivity of the reaction is also improved considerably. The test paper impregnated with the reagents, zinc acetate, sodium nitroprusside and 1 : 10 phenanthroline is successfully used for detection of sulphur dioxide in air upto 0.5 ppm.

Experimental

Reagents: (a) 1M zinc acetate dihydrate in 5% v/v glycerol, (b) 1% w/v solution of sodium nitroprusside, (c) 0.2% w/v solution of 1 : 10 phenanthroline in 50% aqueous ethanol.

All reagents used are of Analytical grade.

Preparation of the Test paper: Test papers are prepared by the following method—Take the above three reagents (a), (b), (c) in 10 ml beakers. Dip Whatman No. 1 filter paper strips (1 × 5 cms) in these solutions serially and dry the paper in a temperature controlled oven at 50–60°. These papers which are cream coloured are stable for few days if kept in well-stoppered dark bottles.

Procedure: Insert a test paper, moistened in glycerol water solution, (5% v/v) in a test paper holder and connect it to a source of suction, fitted with a rotameter. Draw one liter of air through the paper at a rate of 200–250 ml per minute. The colour of test paper turns from cream to brick red and this indicates the presence of sulphur dioxide in the sample.

Results and Discussion

By using 1 : 10 phenanthroline, the method becomes more sensitive than the methods reported by Hand⁵ *et al.*, and Bourbon^{3,4}. In aqueous solution the reagent gives a bulky brick red precipitate with sulphur dioxide. The coloured precipitate is sensitive to pH and is insoluble in common organic solvents as benzene, carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, acetone, ethanol etc. Attempts are being made to stabilise the coloured precipitate in solution and make a quantitative method for determination of sulphur dioxide, by colorimetric/turbidimetric methods.

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